

Heisenberg x-p Uncertainty Relation As a Statement of Spatial Invariance?

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The classical probability for constant momentum (or velocity) $P(x)=1/L$, where L is length, does not specify the value of momentum and so applies to all momenta p . We have argued in previous notes that $1/L$ is a distribution of static objects in L and so $P(x)=P_d(px)P_d(-px)$ where $P_d(px)=\exp(ipx)$. In other words, each $\exp(ipx)$ is associated with the same invariance in x shown by $P(x)$. This property may be quantified by writing: $d/dx (x \exp(ipx)) - x d/dx \exp(ipx) = 1\exp(ipx)$ ((1)) and applies to any p . This math statement seems to demonstrate that for any p and the $\exp(ipx)$ probability form, one ultimately moves along x one constant Δx step at a time, regardless of p .

As a result, one may generalize ((1)) by writing $W(x)=\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ such that $\int W^*(x)W(x)dx=1$. Then: $\int dx W^*(x) \{d/dx (x W) - x d/dx W\} = 1$.

This simply shows that regardless of the weighting of $\exp(ipx)$ s, which is associated with a distribution in both x and p , ultimately the same x to $x+\Delta x$ spatial invariance holds for each $\exp(ipx)$.

The above statement may be quantified by noting that ((1)) is quadratic in $[d/dx, x]$, where $[]$ is a commutator. Other quadratic forms include xx and $d/dx d/dx$ which measure the variance of xx and $d/dx d/dx$. Thus, one should be able to form a relationship linking the variance of x and d/dx with the constant 1 which indicates the same spatial invariance $x \rightarrow x + dx$ for all $\exp(ipx)$. We argue that the Heisenberg x-p uncertainty follows from the above idea. The x variance multiplied by the p variance is linked to the $x \rightarrow x+dx$ spatial invariance which holds for all $\exp(ipx)$ and so is not affected by which $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ one uses.

We suggest that this is an alternative way of thinking of the x-p Heisenberg uncertainty relation. Traditionally, $[d/dx, x]$ is described as measuring x and then p and comparing this with the reverse measuring order.

Spatial Invariance and $\exp(ipx)$

In classical physics one may write: $P(x)dx=dx/L$, where L is length, for constant p momentum (or velocity). This holds for any p . One has spatial invariance and may move from x to $x+dx$, i.e. in constant dx steps, regardless of p .

We have argued in previous notes that $P(x)=1/L$ applies to the distribution of a static object in L . In order to be consistent, we argued that $P(x) = P_d(px) P_d(-px)$, where P_d is a kind of dynamic probability. A solution is: $P_d(px) = \exp(-ipx)$. This probability function is dynamic, but at the same time it is linked to $x \rightarrow x+dx$, where $dx=\text{constant}$ for any p . We suggest that this idea is key to the x-p Heisenberg uncertainty principle.

Relationship Describing Spatial Invariance for $\exp(ipx)$

We wish to write a math expression which shows the $x \rightarrow x+dx$ relationship which holds for any p . We suggest using:

$$d/dx (x \exp(ipx)) - x d/dx (\exp(ipx)) = 1 \exp(ipx) \quad ((2))$$

Given that $\exp(ipx)$ changes in space, we wish to subtract this change to show that $x \rightarrow x+dx$. Thus, ((2)) demonstrates that $x \rightarrow x+dx$ through the value of 1.

$$\text{Explicitly, } d/dx \{x \exp(ipx)\} = \{ (x+dx) \exp(ip(x+dx)) - x \exp(ipx) \} / dx \quad ((3))$$

Keeping only linear terms shows that the 1 in ((2)) is really associated with equally spaced steps dx , or the same spatial invariance for each $\exp(ipx)$.

One may generalize ((2)) by using: $W(x) = \sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx)$ where $\int dx \ W^*(x)W(x)$.

$$\text{Then: } \int dx \ W^*(x) \{ d/dx (x W) - x d/dx W \} = 1 \quad ((4))$$

In other words, 1 appears again because each $\exp(ipx)$ is linked to the same $x \rightarrow x+dx$ spatial invariance. In the case of $W(x)$, however, one has both a distribution in p and x . Any p and x distribution, however, is associated with the same basic spatial invariance ((4)) linked to each $\exp(ipx)$. ((4)), is quadratic in x and d/dx in the sense of $[x, d/dx]$ where $[]$ is the commutator. This suggests writing the overall quadratic function given in (1), i.e.:

$$\int dx \ W^* \{ x + i d/dx \} \{ x - i d/dx \} W = \int dx \ W^* x x W + \int dx \ W^* d/dx d/dx W + \int dx \ W^* i [d/dx, x] W \quad ((5))$$

The last term on the RHS is the spatially invariant one which holds for any W , i.e. is insensitive to weights, i.e. the p or x distribution, while the first two terms are the x and d/dx variances.

As noted in (1), ((5)) should be real, but is also ≥ 0 . (1) notes that it may only have one real root.

(One may see that the first and last terms of ((5)) are positive. The second term may be written as: $\langle -i d/dx W | -i d/dx W \rangle$ which is also positive.)

Using the quadratic formula: $ayy+by + c=0 \rightarrow y = \{-b \pm \sqrt{bb-4ac}\}/2a$ so the one real root is at $bb=4ac$ and so one has:

$$bb \leq 4ac \text{ or: } \text{Var}(xx) \text{Var}(d/dx d/dx) \geq \frac{1}{4} \langle W [d/dx, x] W \rangle^2 \leq \langle W [d/dx, x] W \rangle^2 \quad ((6))$$

Changing d/dx to $-i \hbar d/dx$, this yields the usual p - x Heisenberg uncertainty relationship:

$$\text{Var}(xx) \text{Var}(pp) \geq \hbar^2/4 \quad ((7))$$

Thus, the fact that one may write the spatial invariance property $x \rightarrow x+dx$ in terms of a quadratic, i.e. $[d/dx, x]$ which holds for all $\exp(ipx)$, allows one to link this to $\text{Var}(xx)$ and

$\text{Var}(d/dx \text{ } d/dx)$. Given that $\exp(ipx)$ is the dynamic probability and changes in x , one needs to consider x with $\exp(ipx)$ and then subtract off $x \text{ } d/dx \exp(ipx)$. This leads to the quadratic nature. This $[d/dx, x]$ is a constant for any $\exp(ipx)$ and hence for Integra. $W^* [d/dx, x] W \text{ } dx$.

Conclusion

Traditionally, $[d/dx, x]$ or rather $[-i\hbar d/dx, x]$, is said to represent the difference in measure x first followed by measuring p and subtracting this result from the reverse measurement order. This result is then linked to $\text{Var}(x)\text{Var}(p)$ in the Heisenberg uncertainty relation.

Here we suggest that $\exp(ipx)$ follows from the classical spatial invariance statement $P(x)=1/L$ where L is length. In other words, $x \rightarrow x + dx$, where dx is a constant for any p and $\exp(ipx)$. This statement may be quantified through: $d/dx (x \exp(ipx)) - x \text{ } d/dx \exp(ipx) = 1 \exp(ipx)$ or: $[d/dx, x] \exp(ipx) = 1 \exp(ipx)$ ((8)). We argue that the 1 represents the constant dx which applies to all $\exp(ipx)$. As a result, one may create any $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)$ (which have different $\text{Var}(x)$ and $\text{Var}(p) = \text{Var}(-i\hbar d/dx)$ and the idea of ((8)) still holds as a statement of spatial invariance. Following (1), one may then create the quadratic: $\text{Integral } dx \text{ } W^* (x + id/dx) (x - id/dx) W$ and obtain a quadratic which is real and positive. This means that it has one positive root and $\text{Var}(xx) \text{Var}(d/dx \text{ } d/dx) \geq 1/4 \text{ Integral } W^* i [d/dx, x] W \text{ } dx$. The RHS, however, is the spatial invariant $x \rightarrow x + dx$ statement which holds for all $\exp(ipx)$ and so the weights of $W(x)$ are irrelevant (as long as it is normalized). One thus obtains a relationship linking $\text{Var}(x)\text{Var}(p = -i\hbar d/dx)$ with the spatial invariant statement 1 multiplied by $i\hbar$. We suggest that this is an alternative approach to considering the x - p uncertainty statement.

Reference

1. Rais, J. and van Hees, H. and Greiner, C. Bound State Formation in Time Dependent Potentials (2022) <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2207.04898>